

Invest Game: Investments in Startups in an Entrepreneurship Course

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Abstract

One of the great challenges in Engineering education is to open and foment the interest of learning about the technical core of each course and about complimentary themes that are relevant in the life of an engineer. Among the different approaches applied to implement novel learning methodologies, gamification stands as a promising alternative. This work aims to present Invest Game; a game created to be applied in entrepreneurship courses that have activities based on active learning methodologies. Invest Game aims to allow the learning about financial background and applications of startups through interactions among the students of a given class group within an Academic course. Invest game is applied in three rounds of investment, which are made by different teams that interact among themselves in each course term. This article, in these lines, explains step by step the logics and fundamentals of Invest Game and introduces a real case study of its application in an entrepreneurship course at the Engineering School of Lorena at the University of São Paulo in Brazil. In this course, the students were part of teams, which were named as startups with goals to create a business based on the Sustainable Development Goals for 2030 set by the United Nations. A questionnaire was applied at the end of the term, which demonstrates that, for the majority of the students, the game contributed to: (i) the development of competences about investment; (ii) the enhancement of the deliveries given across the course term; and (iii) the development of the startup they created.

Keywords: Gamification; Entrepreneurship; Investment; Startup; Active Learning Methodologies.

1 Introduction

High percentages of entrepreneurs in a country can be a reference of its economic development. The Global Entrepreneurship Monitor (Bosma et al, 2020) report presents an overview of entrepreneurship around the world. This report revealed that in 2019 the total rate of entrepreneurs in Brazil was 38.7%. It is estimated that about 53 million Brazilians (18-64 years) are involved in some entrepreneurial activity. The total early-stage entrepreneurial activity (TEA) rate was 23.3%; thus, Brazil occupies the 4th position in a ranking with 50 countries participating in the GEM in 2019.

Despite this high number of entrepreneurs, Brazil's National Entrepreneurship Context Index (NECI) is 4, thus placing the country as the 43rd in the ranking of 54 participating economies. The main factors for this classification are the tax and bureaucratic burdens, which are not favorable to the growth of companies, and the low emphasis on actions related to entrepreneurship in pedagogical projects (Bosma et al, 2020).

The same report also presents a general analysis of whether the new companies created in Brazil offer "new" or "old" products and services. The conclusion is that among new Brazilian companies, 98.4% do not offer new products and services. Only 0.6% of these new companies offer new products and services.

Amid constant changes and a future filled with uncertainty, job positions will increasingly demand adaptations and new standards. According to the World Economic Forum, new opportunities undergo rapid changes to meet the technological and economic needs provided by evolution. Like job opportunities, companies are also changing, and due to the great competitiveness of the market, they are increasingly looking for qualified and innovative professionals (WEF, 2020). Among these professionals are Engineers with solid technical backgrounds. Engineers who are committed to the pursuit of excellence. Engineers who are challenged and encouraged to create, innovate, and develop technology-based startups.

Like many countries around the world, Brazil resents technological entrepreneurship. Engineers who have been graduating over the past few years resent an entrepreneurial education that develops skills to motivate them to venture into entrepreneurial activities in the field of technology, whether creating companies, or acting as intrapreneurs in large companies or startups. Aware of this challenge, in 2012 the Lorena School of Engineering of the University of São Paulo (USP), Brazil, introduced an Entrepreneurship course in the curriculum of its majors. This course is mandatory for Production Engineering, Physical Engineering and Chemical Engineering, and optional for Environmental Engineering, Biochemical Engineering and Materials Engineering. The course aims to foster the culture of entrepreneurship, develop entrepreneurial competences, and encourage students to create startups.

Training engineers with an entrepreneurial mindset requires revising traditional models of education, and the Entrepreneurship course created at the Lorena School of Engineering has adopted active learning methodologies since its first class. Higher degree of involvement, dynamism and interaction are fundamental characteristics of this type of methodology, as it uses strategies and techniques aimed at engaging students to take on the role of leaders of their learning (Roig & Stoyanova, 2018; Martinez, 2020).

The use of active methodologies has been encouraged by researchers for their importance and effectiveness in education, since the principles employed by these methods enrich pedagogical dynamics. Thus, in the first principle, students become agents of their own learning, that is, they are the center of the teaching-learning process (Marchesi; Coll & Palacios, 2018). In turn, the teacher becomes the facilitating agent, mediating the learning process and instigating students' knowledge. Thus, the second guiding principle of active methodologies is to encourage student autonomy, which provides benefits for their personal and professional lives (Bai; Hew & Huang, 2020).

There are countless active learning methodologies. Those that have been used in the Entrepreneurship course at the Lorena School of Engineering are peer instruction (Nicol & Boyle, 2003), gamification (Dicheva, Dichev, Agre, & Angelova, 2015), project-based learning (Pereira, Barreto & Pazeti, 2017) and flipped classroom (Stöhr; Demazière & Adawi, 2020).

Gamification, one of these approaches, involves participants in problem-solving through gaming principles. It can be applied digitally (through the use of software) or not digitally (such as with board games) (Jantschgi, Scheff & Erkner-Sacherl, 2020). In general, organizations seek to develop innovative aspects from simulations in contexts that are as close as possible to real life. According to Ramli et al. (2018), the application of experiential learning tools and business simulations in the teaching-learning process enables students to develop skills and competencies that will be required in their professional lives. Gamification principles have been very well explored in entrepreneurial education, because in addition to contributing to learning, they enable students to have new ideas that can yield future ventures (Krajger, Lattacher & Schwarz, 2020).

Invest Game, the central theme of this article, consists of a game created to be applied in the Entrepreneurship courses offered at the Lorena School of Engineering. This course is taught in 15 weekly 100-minute classes. It is led by a professor and a team of 6 mentors, who are undergraduate or graduate students who have knowledge about entrepreneurship from personal experiences on the topic. Students set up teams (referred to as startups) of a maximum of 6 members. Each of the startups must create a business that meets one of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) on the UN Millennium Agenda (United Nations, 2020).

2 Invest Game

Invest Game is a gamified system developed specifically for the Entrepreneurship course of the Lorena School of Engineering, aiming at greater interactivity between all students, as well as enabling learning about startup investments. In addition, it focuses on developing the students' critical analysis competences, creating an environment of healthy competition, and stimulating an improvement in everyone's performance throughout the semester.

Invest Game was inspired by the classic entrepreneurship game show "Shark Tank," a North American show based on the old reality show Dragons' Den (Adalian, 2013), which already has versions in several countries,

such as “Shark Tank Brazil.” The show features aspiring entrepreneurs who present their business idea to a group of potential investors, called “sharks,” who then ask some key questions to better assess the business proposal and decide whether to invest in the company.

Invest Game works based on some of the projects developed in the course, applied in three rounds of investment during the academic semester. The objective of these investment rounds is to enable the use of assessment criteria similar to those used by investors in the real world when making the decision to invest money in new startups.

Each of the three rounds of Invest Game has two stages. The **first stage** consists of feedback for each project developed, delivered through an online form with the criteria to be evaluated using a Likert scale (Likert, 1932). This step is carried out individually by all students, so that everyone knows what the other startups are developing in the course. Students are expected to develop a critical sense, as they will be evaluating startups, including their own. The **second stage** consists of making the investments, which are made in **U\$pins**, a virtual currency created for Invest Game. It has symbolic value, with limits and rules on how it can be used to classify the startups, simulating an investment situation. In this first round of investment, each startup receives 500 U\$pins to invest according to the rules defined in Section 2.4. To make the investment, it is necessary that all students from the same startup get together and analyze their individual assessments made in the first stage, as they must make a decision as a team on the amount they will invest in each startup, using a second online form specific to this stage.

The **course mentors** also invest, in parallel with the activities carried out by the students and startups, in each of the investment rounds. They have 500, 500 and 1000 U\$pins to invest, respectively, in the 1st, 2nd and 3rd investment rounds, following the same rules as the startups.

After each investment round, a general investment ranking is generated, which consists of the sum of the investment made by the startups and the investment made by the mentors. The result is used as a criterion for granting an amount of U\$pins for the next round of investment for the first 5 places, with the additional value granted per placement available in Table 1.

Table1. Grant in U\$pins according to the position in the ranking.

Position in the ranking	Additional Value (in U\$pin)
1st	250
2nd	200
3rd	150
4th	100
5th	50

2.1 First Round

The first stage of the first round of Invest Game consists of posting a video presentation presenting the business model of each of the startups, based on Lean Canvas (Maurya, 2012). This is done through an online platform used by USP. The video must have a maximum duration of three minutes. All students in the class must watch all videos in their class. Then, they must answer an online questionnaire using the Likert scale with the statements presented in Table 2. The scale used was 1 to 5, where 1: strongly disagree and 5: totally agree with each statement. This same scale from 1 to 5 was used in all other questionnaires, based on a Likert scale.

Table 2. Statements of the first round.

The product or service proposed by the startup is highly innovative/original , standing out as a pioneer in the industry in which it intends to operate.
The potential for scalability (accelerated growth) of the proposed business is high and it has a large market in Brazil.
The proposal fully meets one of the 17 SDGs of the UN Millennium Agenda, as established as a fundamental rule of the Entrepreneurship course.
The product or service presented by the startup is a real consumer need .
The pitch was very well done and left no question about the problem that the product/service intends to solve, as well as the proposed solution that it intends to develop.

2.2 Second Round

In the second round of Invest Game, the Minimum Viable Product (Ries, 2020) is presented. The startups will deliver video pitches of 2 minutes at most, presenting their respective MVPs. From this task, all students in the same class must watch all videos and answer fill out the online feedback and investment form. Table 3 presents the statements contained in the MVP feedback form.

Table 3. Statements of the second round.

The prototype developed has the characteristics of an MVP .
The startup has clearly demonstrated that the product delivers value to the customer .
The use of the product by the customer was well explained in the pitch.
The basic functionalities of the product were well clarified in the pitch.
The pitch was very well done and left no question about the product it intends to deliver.

2.3 Third Round

The third round of Invest Game consists of "My Startup," which is a booklet containing essential information about the Startup, such as Visual Identity, Team, Target Audience, Business Model, Monetization and Market. "My Startup" is a summary of the Business Plan that is presented by all startups at the end of the semester. The statements contained in the "My Startup" feedback form are shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Statements of the third round.

The problem is well-defined and is relevant.
The proposed solution really meets the needs of customers.
The proposed market is suitable for the defined problem and the proposed solution.
The proposed indicators are realistic and feasible.
The "My Startup" enables a perfect understanding of the startup's business model .

2.4 Rules

For Invest Game to function, a set of rules was developed seeking the effective participation of students in the game, considering that this can generate a bonus in the course final grade. In addition, the rules are also important as they instruct about the investments made by each startup. The main rules of Invest Game are:

- Each startup can invest up to 30% in its own business in each of the three investment rounds. If the investment exceeds 30%, it will be considered NULL.
- All investment funds must be used in each round by all startups to invest in up to 5 startups, including their own.
- Each startup can invest a maximum of 50% in a single startup, except their own, in each round of investment.
- The startup will lose 10% of its investment amount for each member who does not watch all the videos and completely fill out the pitch feedback form for the other startups.

2.5 Awards

Invest Game has two types of awards:

- Based on the ranking generated at the end of the semester, which will be obtained by the sum of all the investments of the mentors and students made in the three rounds. Each of the students from startups in first, second and third place will have an increase of 1.0 point; 0.70 points; and 0.50 points in their final course grade, respectively.
- Based on the mentor investment ranking, generated at the end of the three rounds. Each of the students from startups who invested at least 550 U\$pins in the startup ranked first in the mentor ranking receives an increase of 0.70 points in their final course grade.

It is worth mentioning that the grades in the course go from 0 (zero) to 10.0 (ten).

3 Application of Invest Game

Invest Game was applied for the first time in 2020 in 4 classes of the Entrepreneurship course, with 2 classes in the first semester and 2 classes in the second semester. The classes had an average of 70 students. For the purposes of presenting the results of the application of Invest Game, only one class will be presented, taught in the first semester of 2020.

The results and analyzes presented in this section refer to the five best evaluated startups by students and mentors (section 3.1). An interesting coincidence is that these were the same startups that received the most investments (section 3.2). Startup 1 developed a used clothing sales platform. Startup 2 developed a platform with the objective of connecting garbage collectors with social organizations that operate in the same area. Startup 3 developed an application to guide the creation of a vegetable garden at home. Startup 4 developed a piezoelectric system to generate energy through the mechanical impact generated by walking and startup 5 developed a device to reduce water waste in public drinking fountains.

Invest Game was applied entirely online through the Google Meet platform, used by the University of São Paulo. The Google Forms tool was used to collect data from the various online questionnaires answered by students in the feedback and investment rounds. The rounds took place between March and June 2020 as detailed in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The rounds.

3.1 Stage 1 – Feedback from all students

At the end of each round, online forms were made available for students and mentors to assess the work of each startup in that investment round.

Table 5 presents the averages of each feedback round, for analysis. Only the five startups that had the best performance in the group are presented. This table shows the assessments of all students and mentors in the three investment rounds throughout the semester.

Table 5: Result of the startup assessment feedback carried out by the mentors and students in the 3 rounds.

Startup	1st Round		2nd Round		3rd Round	
	Students	Mentors	Students	Mentors	Students	Mentors
1	4,23	4,13	4,43	4,54	3,95	3,92
2	4,03	3,77	4,21	4,20	4,04	4,05
3	3,95	3,87	3,91	4,10	3,93	3,91
4	4,10	4,77	3,63	3,66	3,65	3,64
5	3,70	3,13	4,24	4,19	4,01	3,98

As can be seen in the results shown in Table 5, the main difference in scores between mentors and students happened in the first feedback round (0.67 in the assessment for Startup 4). In the second round, the maximum difference decreased to 0.19 (see assessment of Startup 3). And in the last round, there was no significant difference.

A possible explanation for the difference of 0.67 in startup 4 in the first round, may be due to the greater expertise of the mentors in relation to the students for the solution presented regarding the generation of piezoelectric energy. It is possible that this theme for being very specific was unknown to some students who were taking the course.

In the second round, there is an increase in mentors' grades. A possible cause could be the fact that the projects were already with a greater degree of maturity because they had already developed the MVP.

The results for the third round, on the other hand, show the smallest differences in grades between students and mentors. A possible explanation for the reduction in the difference between the mentors' and students' assessment score is the greater expertise of the mentors to evaluate startups according to their previous experiences in the area. However, throughout the semester, students learned to improve their assessment competences, so that in the third round, the assessment of students and mentors was similar.

Thus, Invest Game is not only a game that presents and brings Engineering students closer to startup investment rounds, but also increases their assessment competences.

3.2 Stage 2 – Startup Investments

After students completed the feedback form, an investment form was made available for each startup to inform how many U\$pins they wished to invest in other startups. Figure 2 shows the investments made by students and mentors in five startups of the first semester of 2020.

Figure 2. Section of Investments made by mentors and students in each of the 3 rounds.

There is a discrepancy in the investment in Startup 1 in all rounds. The discrepancy in the 1st and 2nd rounds may be associated with the form of communication used by this startup. The presentation made was much more attractive than that of the other startups. In addition, their business (used clothing sales platform) is something very familiar to investors, in this case students.

Specifically in the 3rd round of investment, it can be assumed that the award given by Invest Game to the startup ranked in second place, influenced investments in Startup 1. This may have happened since startups that invested 550 U\$pins in 1st place in the overall ranking of mentors, would receive 0.7 points in the final grade of the course.

3.3 Assessment of Invest Game

After Invest Game was applied in the first and second semesters of 2020, an online form was made available for students to assess the game as a whole.

For this, 5 key performance indicators were defined to verify the assertiveness of the game, using a Likert scale as explained previously in Section 2.1. In addition, a space for comment and suggestions was also made available as an option, for a qualitative analysis.

Concerned with getting answers with no bias, students were only asked to name the Startup of which they were members. Table 6 presents the statements contained in the form:

Table 6 – Invest Game statements analyzed by students according to a Likert scale.

1	Invest Game added value to the Entrepreneurship course.
2	Invest Game helped to understand how investments in startups are made.
3	The investment rounds were relevant to my learning process in the course .
4	The feedback given during the program was important for the improvement of subsequent projects .
5	Invest Game contributed to the development of my startup .

In Figure 3, the averages obtained for each of the 5 statements presented in Table 6 are represented in bars. In this graph, the orange bars refer to the results of the classes of the 1st semester of 2020, and in blue, the results of the classes of the 2nd semester of 2020:

Figure 3: Invest Game assessment averages in 2020.

As can be seen in the graph, Invest Game had average assessments above 3.5. Thus, students more often agreed than disagreed that Invest Game had a positive impact on the course and development of projects. The sample of this research was 80 and 45 students, from the 1st and 2nd semester of 2020, respectively, who answered this questionnaire voluntarily.

This result suggests that the feedbacks given during Invest Game contributed positively to the students, adding value to the course and contributing to the development of the startups.

The responses to statements 2 and 3, despite having averages higher than 3.5, present a specific problem that must be solved in future applications of the game. They indicate that there was not a very clear perception of students in relation to investment in startups and their relevance to the learning process in the course. Thus, as a solution, Invest Game must be better contextualized within the course projects, making reference to the reality of the market, in addition to changing the way of disseminating the results, which were not usually discussed in class.

Below, some of the comments received through the forms:

1. "I think the coolest about the Invest Game was the class - that is, people outside the idea - assessing how the startup was doing, which is very valid. Maybe what can be improved is to better represent a real investment." (Student from the 1st semester).
2. "I didn't like it, because the feedbacks were positive, but when it came to investing, no one did, so we didn't know what we were doing wrong." (Student from the 2nd semester)
3. "Invest Game served to motivate us and to increase the quality of the activities we did." (Student from the 2nd semester)

Like all didactic methodologies, there are positive points and points to be improved. The result of the assessment points out that Invest Game seems to have achieved its objective, since it engaged and motivated students to apply themselves and observe what was being developed by their classmates.

Observing comment 2, the plausible solution is to add a short comment section on the investment form and carrying out a presentation in class clearly comparing the scores and investments of the round, as discussed in this article.

4 Conclusion

The Invest Game was applied to the Entrepreneurship course at the Lorena School of Engineering – USP in 2020. The focus of the game was to develop learning about investments in startups, as well as simulate investment rounds within a university environment. Through the Invest Game, the Entrepreneurship course addressed not only entrepreneurial training, but also knowledge about investments in startups. The surveys carried out at the end of each semester found a good adhesion of the students to the game, which contributed to a better development of projects by the students throughout the semester.

Invest Game proved to be a good initiative. The data collected suggest an increase in the students' learning competences. The game is a good alternative for the practical teaching of investments in startups, which can be applied in other courses and in an adapted way with the purpose of spreading entrepreneurial education.

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